

Chances and Pitfalls of the Point Merge Concept – A design Optimization Framework with a Case Study for Leipzig/Halle Airport on Noise, Capacity and Flight Efficiency

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Abstract— This paper presents a comprehensive design strategy to unlock the full potential of Point-Merge-Systems (PMS) as aircraft approach sequencing and merging concept. As various existing PMS implementations suffer deficits in either capacity or operational efficiency, we propose a multi-objective optimization model, linked to a Monte-Carlo Agent Based simulation for verification and a noise computation module to include all external effects into the design. We show that the concept delivers promising performance improvements over historic approach procedure designs - covering both PMS and trombone - for a preliminary use case application at Leipzig/Halle Airport (EDDP), Germany. We propose to couple the design concept with a pre-sequencing component focusing on robust continuous descent operations, using optimal control.

Keywords: *point merge system, multi-objective optimization, sequencing, metering, merging, flight efficiency, noise abatement*

I. MOTIVATION AND STRUCTURE

Multi-objective capacity versus efficiency considerations, determined by economic (min. fuel), environmental (min. emissions incl. noise), and safety (maintaining minimum separation) performance targets are becoming increasingly important with the growing public interest in green operations and accompanying regulatory activities [1]. The *point merge system* (PMS) was initially developed in 2006 by EUROCONTROL as an enabler infrastructure for efficient sequencing and spacing [2] and considered as valuable contribution to both green and economically efficient operations. However, implementations so far have not achieved larger acceptance, often due to perceived significant airspace requirements linked to procedures with excessive track miles.

Initial thoughts on calibrating a PMS to local requirements towards capacity and flight efficiency as centrally competing design parameter by mainly adopting sequencing leg length and their distance to the *merge point* (MP) were thus found too

limiting (e.g., past implementations for Leipzig, Paris, Oslo airports, see also section I.A). Rather, PMS performance in terms of capacity and efficiency – like other approach concepts – was seen to be impacted by many more design details. To determine the ‘best’ PMS design for a dedicated airport environment, we propose a multi-objective optimization model to include this large set of parameters. To deal with uncertainty in demand pattern and traffic throughput, we embed a Monte-Carlo Agent-Based simulation [2] for verification of the multi-objective optimization and an offline aircraft noise immission assessment following ECAC Doc. 29 [3]. Due to the complexity of the resulting model, we decided to apply it first expert driven to Leipzig/Halle Airport (EDDP) as a use case. EDDP is considered ideal for this prototyping activity characterized by a robust traffic demand pattern with dedicated peak loads during night and based on a rather homogenous and stable traffic mix with European Air Transport (EAT, fully DHL-owned) as the dominant local aircraft operator especially during that peak time.

We executed a sensitivity analysis on the central operational and design-related parameter to prove stability of the computed performance as being presented in this paper.

Beyond the use case, we present a complementing strategy to cover vertical flight efficiency (VFE) aspects along the PMS design process, starting with a tailored top of descent per single flight allocation. This is conceptually kept outside the multi-objective optimization, as VFE optimization requires a much broader geometry to allow covering the full descent. We declare this activity as a pre-sequencing technique using optimal control (OC). OC allows us to deal with constraints formulated as differential equations, inherent to describe the aircraft’s equation of motion (EoM). Also, it allows for robust optimization using data ensemble strategies, to capture uncertain but sensitive descent parameters such as the vertical wind profile in 4D: Explicitly, we suggest controlling the descent angle and the approach speed, calculated by means of differential equations to

maximize VFE. This function would well complement current Arrival Management (AMAN) decision support systems.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section I consolidates current PMS performance achievements towards capacity and efficiency. Section II introduces the multi-objective optimization concept to allow section III to present the PMS redesign use case at Leipzig/Halle. Section IV concludes with the performance of the new design. Section V discusses the introduction of a pre-sequencing function aiming for continuous descents, using optimal control to allow section VI to summarize and look out.

II. STATE OF THE ART

A. Design Parameters from Existing PMS

Over the course of the 2010s, multiple PMS had been implemented, starting at Oslo (EGNM, 2011) and Dublin (EIDW, 2012), reaching out to airports with multiple runway configurations towards the end of the decade, such as Kula Lumpur (WMKK, 3 runways, 2017) [4], Istanbul (LTFM, 3 runways, 2018), or Shanghai (ZSPD, 4 runways, 2020).

The initiating EUROCONTROL team has reviewed the global advances periodically and continually provided guidance on design options with scientific papers [5–8] and a summarizing technical document [9]. Learning from the experiences, a published ‘shortest route’ for fuel planning and additional support points for direct approaches to the MP – effectively skipping the sequencing legs during low traffic loads – were added as a recommendation. More recently, a so-called ‘double point merge’ has recently been added to the concept [10]. Also recently, the authors classify the approach procedures in existence, using ADS-B surveillance data and computer vision [11].

Scandinavian researchers have studied the performance of the Oslo (EGNM) implementation in terms of sequencing, flight efficiency, and resulting aircraft noise [12], also in comparison to other PM implementations such as Dublin (EIDW) and other sequencing techniques such as the ‘trombone’ vectoring pattern practiced in Vienna (LOWW) and Frankfurt/Main (EDDF). Using dynamic programming to optimize flight tracks and profiles, flight efficiency and noise metrics are compared for various levels of optimization. However, these and other works from ENAC et al [13, 14] are limited to performance assessment and optimization of a given PMS design.

The Hungarian ATC has developed a multi-point merge system based on FAA T-bar topology and an accompanying advisory tool called *Merge-Strip* [15]. This is considered a valuable addition to the concept of operations, towards a higher level of automation (decision support), but presumably limited to single runway configurations and low to medium traffic loads. Analyses for Istanbul *Havalimani* airport (LTFM) and Kuala Lumpur (WMKK), focus on the concept’s design to multiple parallel runway configurations [4, 16], clearly highlighting the growing complexity of the design process all around the globe.

In summary, we conclude that the major design options are number and placing of merge points, orientation, opening angle and radii of the associated PMS, resulting in full, partial and no

overlap, which in turn lead to various interdependencies that do affect especially vertical flight efficiency (VFE).

When assessing the aeronautical information publications (AIP, ‘approach charts’) of PMS implementations worldwide, we further conclude that one MP per runway, 20 to 25 NM radius to SL with opening angles around 90 degrees are typical. Notable deviations exist if the airspace is unconfined, and noise restrictions do not apply. This is usually the case if PMS are placed over water (e.g., Dublin, Tokyo). The guidelines [9] further recommend smaller opening angles to limit the variability of the wind component and dissociated structures to allow for independent airborne descent optimizations heading for continuous descent operations (CDO).

B. PMS Design Optimization

While automated PMS optimization methods have improved air traffic efficiency, no universally applicable PMS design optimization framework has been established, yet. Current approaches rely on case-specific tuning, with a subset of all variables such as merge point location, sequencing leg opening angles, and range, all requiring manual adaptation.

Hardell et al. developed a Mixed Integer Programming (MIP) framework for automated traffic synchronization, which enhances sequencing and reduces environmental impact by optimizing delay times [21]. However, the placement of merge points and the design of sequencing legs remain highly dependent on local aviation conditions. Dönmez et al. introduced a stochastic metaheuristic approach for the dynamic utilization of sequencing legs in the Parallel-Point Merge System (P-PMS) at Istanbul Airport [17]. By adapting fully overlapped, partially overlapped, and fully dislocated leg configurations to reflect the best traffic fluctuations, this model aims at optimizing aircraft sequencing while reducing fuel consumption. Their topographical optimization integrates mathematical models with heuristics, minimizing re-sequencing needs, thus aiming for robust traffic management specific to the airport.

Figure 1: HFE and VFE assessment of recorded flight trajectories compared to a reference trajectory [18]

C. Flight Efficiency and CO₂ Emission

Metrics to assess horizontal & vertical flight efficiency (HFE/VFE) have long been established [19]. Pasutto and Zeghal [18] focus on efficiency strategies during descent, covering both lateral and vertical geometric and kinetic considerations. When adopting the geometric ideal trajectory to operational and – at low altitudes – environmental constraints, a quasi-ideal hence

realistic minimum-cost flight trajectory is typically used as reference (see Figure 1), and subsequent inefficiencies in flight execution, reflecting the impact of e.g. adverse weather that day, network and air traffic control restrictions etc.. They all can be quantified using flight performance assessment [20]. Underlying logics as the ‘improved’ Boeing Fuel Flow Method (BFFM2) [21, 22] or EUROCONTROL Base of Aircraft Data (BADA4) [23] rely on the ICAO Engine Emissions Databank (EEDB).

The efficiency assessment can further be quantified in terms of operational delay resp. adherence to the required time of arrival (RTA), excess fuel burn [18], or as combined approaches referring to a adequately weighted multi-objective cost function of the underlying optimization scheme [24].

D. Airspace and Runway Capacity

To achieve maximum arrival runway throughput, both runway occupancy time (ROT) and inter-arrival time (IAT) should be minimized, based on the airspace characteristics given and approach procedures in place. Further, minimum (wake vortex) aircraft separation [25] set constraints to the minimization objective. Finally, aircraft-specific approach speeds per flap setting inherently affect minimum achievable spacing of aircraft in time. Typically, the resulting ‘practical’ runway capacity is derived from this strategy by assuming quasi minimum spacing adherence and a timely maximum average delay per aircraft during approach (e.g., 4 min). The ratio of $\text{MAX}(\text{ROT}, \text{IAT})_{\text{ideal}}$ and $\text{MAX}(\text{ROT}, \text{IAT})_{\text{recorded}}$ leads to the runway utilization rate ≤ 1 or throughput. The ratio is consequently impacted by the distance of the sequencing or metering point (MP) to the runway threshold (the ‘common flight segment’), since downstream that point, the sequence is fixed. For PMS designs, this segment is beginning at the MP.

Figure 2: Typical timely fluctuation of the IAT at a runway with variable traffic mix and manual traffic sequencing [26]

To quantify the quality on how well an arrival sequence is statistically established, the variance of the IAT has often been subject to studies, e.g., [26, 27]. Figure 2 confirms the complexity of this task, expressed by a significant fluctuation of the IAT over time. A similar comparison of PM vs. Trombone approach procedures with equivalent results is found in [28]. It confirms that short common flight segments are in favor of effective runway capacity utilization.

E. Noise Exposure

Designing approach procedures nowadays require strict adherence to noise abatement strategies to find public acceptance. A key contribution to minimizing aircraft noise is to keep aircraft longest at high altitudes and avoid horizontal flight segments (level-offs) along the descent as far as safety requirements are covered. In PMS, horizontal flight segments occur on the sequencing legs and downstream on the intermediate approach segment, the latter however being independent from PMS, but following safety requirements laid down in ICAO PANS OPS. PMS can therefore generally be considered noise mitigating compared to Trombone designs, if the legs are placed further out and at higher altitudes > 8.000 ft. Also, they are considered as an enabler of CDO [29]. From the noise and VFE perspective, Sequencing legs should be located as far away from large town, and technically from MP, as possible. It should be noticed that the contrary is true for achieving high HFE figures!

To quantify the noise immissions resulting from any PMS design, we refer to ECAC Doc 29 [3] as the guidance material. Relying on demographic data, it should not be incorporated in the optimization at full detail. Instead, a simplified noise immission estimation will be used. The detailed noise assessment will run out the optimization. In the section III, we present the developed PMS layout optimization concept.

III. MULTI-CRITERIA OPTIMAL PMS DESIGN

A. Problem Statement

The intent of a PMS design is to provide efficient aircraft sequencing and separation procedures during descent & approach. Vertical separation between aircraft is supported by distinct flight level allocations to the ‘sequencing legs’ SL which are centered around the MP, itself being linked to a dedicated runway & direction. Lateral separation is supported by adequate waypoints on the legs. Whichever waypoint is selected by the ATCO to clear the aircraft to the MP; lateral separation can easily be monitored. Conflict free trajectories are achieved by allocating higher flight levels to inner sequencing legs, if multiple legs are implemented. Downstream of the MP, the aircraft sequence is fixed.

The set of decisive parameters for a PMS design satisfying all local requirements is consequently manifold, going beyond SL placement and radius determination: E.g., the location of the MP is sensitive to the achievable runway throughput, as closing and opening effects due to varying approach speeds downstream the MP affect throughput (see also section I.D). Vertically, both the level allocation scheme to sequencing legs and the horizontal flight requirements on these legs strongly affect VFE resp. full CDO implementation, with exponential costs with decreasing SL altitude [30].

A comprehensive PMS design for a multi-runway system with n runways, represented as the set $I = \{1, \dots, n\}$, shall account for numerous interdependent parameters for each runway $i \in I$. Each runway is further associated with a set of possible sequencing legs, denoted as $\text{SL}_i = \{\text{SL}_{i,1}, \text{SL}_{i,2}, \dots, \text{SL}_{i,j}\}$, where j represents the number of sequencing legs assigned to runway i . The parameters toggling PMS performance are (see Figure 3):

- location of the lateral center of gravity CG_i of the PMS considering airspace constraints, minimum radius $r_{MIN\ i}$ and minimum opening angle $\Theta_{MIN\ i}$ of the number j of $SL_{i,j}$, so to represent a typical PMS area size to accommodate MP and SL
- location of the MP_i best satisfying the weighted objectives $MP_{OPT\ i}$, $d_{MIN\ FAF\ i}$ and $\alpha_{MIN\ i}$
- track length $d_{FAF\ i}$ from MP_i over compulsory Intercept points ($IP_{i,k}$) to final approach fix (FAF_i)
- intercept angle α_i of MP_i to the final approach track, (which may include intercept points in between forming a trombone-style segment as constraints),
- opening angle Θ_i (width), number j and direction of use) of sequencing leg(s),
- radius $r_i \geq r_{MIN\ i}$ from the inner sequencing leg to MP_i , defining the minimum achievable track length,
- flight level allocation(s) $FL_{SL\ i,j}$ to sequencing leg(s) and number k of turn points $TP_{i,j,k}$ on those,
- holding capacity $HoldCap_{SL_i}$ of all SL satisfying the anticipated peak traffic demand input (typically a statistical representative),
- noise abatement.

Figure 3: PMS design for $n=1$ runways with incoming traffic from waypoint 'AP'. Dotted lines and waypoint will be the result of the optimization problem, while solid elements are given.

B. Model Formulation

We define a mathematical formulation of this multi-criteria optimization problem with a resulting objective function, given pre-set weights for the competing goals minimum distance to fly (w_1), maximum capacity (w_2) and noise abatement (w_3), based on a predicted average and peak traffic demand. These objectives can be conflicting with each other; consequently, trade-offs may exist. As a result, a set of Pareto optimal solutions, rather than a single solution, can be found.

Figure 3 illustrates a single runway PMS design procedure, simplified in a sense that potential intercept point IP [31] are not shown. Let $MP = (x_{MP}, y_{MP}, z_{MP})$ denote the MP , defined by its horizontal coordinates x_{MP} , y_{MP} and its altitude z_{MP} relative to RWY threshold elevation and representing the position from which on the aircraft sequence is fixed while aircraft are proceeding to the $FAF = (x_{FAF}, y_{FAF}, z_{FAF})$. Aircraft enter the

procedure at the Arrival Point $AP = (x_{AP}, y_{AP}, z_{AP})$. towards the Entry Point $EP = (x_{EP}, y_{EP}, z_{EP})$ as begin of the innermost sequencing leg (SL), defined as arc with radius r and variable opening angle Θ . The trajectory options range from the shortest path $AP-EP-MP-FAF-RWY$, potentially enriched by IPs to the longest path with additional length given by the full procedure, passing over $LP = (x_{LP}, y_{LP}, z_{LP})$ with $z_{LP} = z_{EP}$. The FAF is located on the extended centerline of the runway at a pre-set distance according to ICAO standards [31], forming the reference of the cartesian coordinate system ($x=0, y=0, z=0$). Variables (waypoints) and PMS characteristics are formatted dotted in Figure 4, input parameters solid. The PMS is geometrically referenced by its center of gravity $CG=(x_{CG}, y_{CG}, z_{CG})$, the radius r , the position MP of and the opening angle Θ .

The optimization of a RWY direction specific PMS design thus comprises:

Decision variables

$MP, CG, LP, EP, IP \in \mathbb{R}^3$, each described by their cartesian coordinates (x,y,z)

$r \in \mathbb{R}^+, \theta \in [0, 2\pi]$

Parameter

$AP, FAF \in \mathbb{R}^3$, each described by their coordinates (x,y,z)

$\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^+$ between $MP \rightarrow FAF$ and extended runway centerline ($y=0$); $\alpha_{max}=45^\circ$

$\beta \in \mathbb{R}^+$ between $AP \rightarrow EP$ and $EP \rightarrow MP$, $\beta_{max}=90^\circ$

$\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^+$ as best glide path as a function of the aircraft's aerodynamic quality, e.g., 3°

The optimization model employs a multi-criteria objective function as defined in Equation 1, where X represents the set of decision vectors x . Each x constitutes a feasible candidate solution for the entire PMS multi-runway system, which consists of multiple runway-sequencing-leg pairs (Equation 2).

Each pair operates its own set of parameters, variables and capacity dynamics, but interdependence between PMS systems can occur. The target function can be prioritized differently using weighting factors w_i , where $\sum_i w_i = 1$. The term $f_1(x)$ minimizes the shortest path, called distance d , including potential IPs (Eq. 3). $f_2(x)$ (Eq. 4) maximizes capacity L by the number of additional aircraft that can be held on j sequencing legs for all $rwys$, defined by $L_i = \sum_j (r_j \cdot \theta_i)$, where the inverse is used for minimization formulation. $f_3(x)$ minimizes the aviation induced noise, where a noise immission index is computed for each cell c of grid C (Eq. 5).

$$\min_{x \in X} W(x) = w_1 f_1(x) + w_2 f_2(x) + w_3 f_3(x) \quad (1)$$

$$x = U_{i \in I, j \in J} [MP_{i,j}, CG_i, EP_{i,j}, IP_i, r_{i,j}, \theta_{i,j}] \quad (2)$$

$$f_1 = \sum_{i \in I, j \in J} (d_{entry} + d_{FAF})_{i,j} \quad (3)$$

$$f_2 = -L = \sum_{i \in I, j \in J} (r_{i,j} \cdot \theta_i) \quad (4)$$

$$f_3 = \sum_{c \in C} ImmissionIndex_c \quad (5)$$

Further constraints

$$\frac{z_{EP} - z_{MP}}{\tan(\gamma)} = r \quad (6)$$

$$\sqrt{(x - x_{MP})^2 + (y - y_{MP})^2} = r, \quad z = z_{EP} \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha = \arccos\left(\frac{x_{FAF} - x_{MP}}{|FAF - MP|}\right) \leq \alpha_{max} \quad (8)$$

$$\beta = \arccos\left(\frac{(EP - AP) \cdot (MP - EP)}{|EP - AP| \cdot |MP - EP|}\right) \leq \beta_{max} \quad (9)$$

Equation 6 determines the radius r of the arc from the altitude difference between EP and MP , maintaining a descent angle γ . According to Eq. 7, the arc lies on a circular line of radius r with MP as its center. The angular constraints Eq. 8 and Eq. 9 satisfy that $\alpha \leq 90^\circ$ and $\beta \leq 45^\circ$ following ICAO PANS-OPS [31] procedure design criteria.

Since the objectives f_1 , f_2 , and f_3 are inherently conflicting (i.e., increasing capacity by enlarging the opening angle Θ leads to increased minimum trajectory length and so to reduced operational efficiency), the problem requires multi-objective optimization techniques, typically resulting in a Pareto front. To find good candidates for the solution vector x , gradient-based or simulation-based metaheuristic approaches, such as Genetic Algorithms (GA) or Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), are suited for complex, event-dependent problems. However, in optimizing the PMS configuration for multiple runways, counteracting effects must be carefully managed. For instance, interactions between traffic streams may require adjustments to sequencing legs (arc opening angle) or entry points, typically impacting efficiency. Additionally, high utilization of a single PMS can reduce the practical capacity (definition see below) of another due to shared runway (resource) constraints and/or

required traffic synchronization. Also, aligning one PMS with runway operations may introduce delays in other parts of the system, thereby affecting overall efficiency. To mitigate these interdependencies, we integrate dynamic traffic simulations as an evaluation resp. verification function within the multi-criteria optimization loop (see Figure 4). This allows for continuous performance assessment and iterative adjustments to sequencing leg structures and merge strategies.

Allover, the PMS ‘ensemble’ for an airport with multiple runways is being tailored for safe (capacitated) and efficient (most direct paths) handling of all traffic streams feeding the different runways. Interdependencies based on e.g., shared airspace, operational constraints, and runway system are considered while to

- minimize fuel burn by most direct paths (w_1), maximize throughput by providing sufficient capacity in the PMS (w_2), minimize noise immissions (w_3),
- and account for potential conflicts and dependencies.

C. Solving the Multi-Objective Optimization

For a multi-runway system, the optimization process is conducted iteratively for each runway. This process aims to consider optimal traffic demand allocations to dedicated runways (e.g., geographically). If the verification logic as shown in Figure 4 while assessing throughput, delay, average track length, and noise immissions at regulatory detail following ECAC Doc. 29 [3] fails to meet predefined performance criteria, the related design strategy will be rejected, else stored as candidate solution. The process continues until all perturbations have been assessed, ultimately converging to the most suitable PMS configuration for the given (multi-)runway system.

Figure 4: Workflow of the PMS design optimization process considering multiple objectives: flight efficiency, capacity and emissions

Figure 4 illustrates the proposed model integrating a multi-criteria optimization loop and a verification process using agent-based traffic model simulation (ABMS) [2, 32] and noise assessment. The overarching objective is to generate PMS configurations that optimize fuel efficiency, capacity, and noise metrics while considering operational constraints and traffic dependencies. This process and evaluation incorporate time-series demand data and traffic sequencing logic as inputs. The optimization process relies on historical and forecasted traffic demand, including arrival rates, aircraft types, and sector entry times. These inputs guide sequencing decisions and PMS adaptations based on traffic fluctuations. The ABMS, fed with an arrival flight test data set, evaluates the system performance towards capacity through separation maintenance assessment, and operational (fuel) efficiency through average flight path length assessment (see also Figure 8). Dynamic adjustments (of the agents) to sequencing legs (SLs) and MPs reflect realistic, day-to-day strategies of Air Traffic Controller (ATCO) to generally achieve good system performance while keeping rule-based constraints to foster runway throughput. Finally, a full-scale noise assessment function verifies compliance with pre-set noise goals, thus implicitly validating the approximated noise computation inside the optimization loops. This summarizes the **Verification** (shown on the bottom left-hand side in Figure 4) consisting of the ABMS and the detailed noise assessment using legacy frameworks.

Should the verification step fail, i.e., the candidate solution does not meet pre-set thresholds for efficiency, capacity or – yet still approximated - noise immissions, the PMS design is iteratively refined and fed back to the multi-criteria optimization.

Multiple PMS structures may feed traffic into a single runway, or alternatively, multiple PMS systems may serve multiple runways. The assignment of arriving aircraft to specific runways is managed through a pre-sequencing function, which operates independently of the PMS optimization, is taken as input to the model.

Along the optimization process, each runway is treated as an independent entity, but the overall system must account for interactions and dependencies between the PMS per runway direction, when traffic metering is being organized to every runway. These potential interactions include shared airspace constraints, runway synchronization requirements, and cross-effects on throughput or delay caused by temporarily high utilization of a single PMS. Each PMS feeds traffic to its assigned runway or set of runways, and the optimization process iteratively refines parameters following the sequence in section II.A and II.B, until convergence is achieved. Compliant spacing and sequencing across the PMS are verified using the ABMS, noise the legacy framework

In the **Runway-Specific PMS Optimization Loop** (outer loop on the right-hand side in Figure 4), PMS parameters as solution vector x — CG_i , MP_i , r_i , SL_i ($FL_{i,j}$ and Θ_i) are iteratively adjusted for a runway specific r_i . These adjustments consider airspace constraints, a minimum radius r_{min} , and a minimum lateral angle Θ_{min} . The loop continues until the w_x weighted objective function is minimized and identifies the best CG_i , forming the foundation for subsequent optimization of the

related MP_i location: The merge point MP_i is positioned so to ensure an intercept angle $\alpha \geq \alpha_{min}$ to the final approach track from FAF downstream to runway threshold, potentially supplemented by additional intercept points IP, if required to correctly design the approach procedure [31]. Given the significant impact of the MP geographic position and altitude on noise emissions, a noise approximation model is used during the iterative optimization process. This to avoid the computational overhead of running the full-scale, non-convergent noise assessment which instead will be executed as part of the verification process as explained above.

Building on these two previous loops, the third loop aims to find the ideal vertical positioning of the sequencing legs $FL_{SL_{i,j}}$ to ensure compliance with airspace constraints, separation adherence, and – ideally – allow for full CDO descent procedures. This adjustment is based on aircraft performance characteristics and aims to maximize the feasibility of achieving optimal CDO profiles. The number of sequencing legs j is determined by the achievable throughput identified in previous iterations, as well as their lateral positioning. Finally, in the fourth loop, the lateral configuration of sequencing legs ($\Theta_{SL_{i,j}}$) is optimized. This step considers the holding capacity ($holdingCap_{SL_{i,j}}$) and the length of the sequencing legs, which are determined by their opening angle Θ_i . Together, these loops aim at balancing system efficiency, capacity, and noise impact across all runways in the multi-runway system following their given respective weights w_1 , w_2 , and w_3 . The optimization for the multi-runway PMS can be concluded as Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Simulation-based single PMS design optimization process, addressing efficiency and capacity

Init $MP_i^0, CG_i^0, EG_i^0, SL_{ij}(\Theta, FL), r_i \forall$ runways i

While (performance thresholds not met) (Verification Loop)

For runway i

Determine $CG_{i,OPTIMAL}$

Adjust $MP_{i,OPTIMAL}$ to minimize intercept angle α and distance d_{FAF} , incorporating approximations of noise

Adjust $FL_{SL_{i,j}}$ for airspace constraints, safe separations, and CDO feasibility

Adjust $\Theta_{SL_{i,j}}$ for $holdingCap_{SL_{i,j}}$ and sequencing leg length

Validate constraints, add penalties if necessary

Evaluate $E(x) \rightarrow (f_1(x), f_2(x), f_3(x))$

Verify if $W(x) = w_1 f_1(x) + w_2 f_2(x) + w_3 f_3(x)$ is minimized for all runways i

If not: Update x (GA: crossover, mutation, and selection)

Output PMS optimal x^* and $f_1(x^*), f_2(x^*), f_3(x^*)$

The layered optimization logic presented will be demonstrated in a use case study in the section IV.

IV. USE CASE: PMS AT LEIPZIG/HALLE AIRPORT

We applied the optimization concept to a PMS re-design for EDDP, using an expert driven approach for initial testing. This

means that the optimization was not yet implemented in a solver environment (such as Gurobi) but executed computer-assisted step by step. EDDP already featured once a PMS – from 2015 to 2019 [33] – before again receiving a conventional trombone approach procedure. The historic PMS design was judged to neither provide sufficient capacity during peak times, nor efficient (direct) routing outside peak periods. This traffic demand fluctuation in EDDP is considered to remain following a year 2032 traffic forecast from DHL, EDDP cargo home carrier (see Figure 5).

In particular, the historic PMS was not designed to allow for independent parallel approaches, as it only consisted of one single MP per runway direction. The consecutive trombone system then allowed for independent parallel approaches and so provided the required capacity during peak times to DHL, but came along with a noise malus, as the approach altitude was fixed at IAF, thus consisting of lengthy horizontal flight segments at relatively low altitudes (5,000 ft to 6,000 ft).

Figure 5: Use case EDDP: Traffic Forecast 2032, Inbounds, representative day, source: DHL

Based on the decisive parameters shown in section III.B, we consequently were heading for a new PMS design for each runway (4 in total), thus containing 2 entry points (EP), respectively 2 SL, each.

Figure 6 shows the cell-wise cost weighting output of the initial, outer optimization loop ‘CG placement’ for the EDDP example runway direction 26L with already added fundamental PMS design components, primarily serving traffic from south:

Figure 6: Use case EDDP Step 1: CG optimization for RWY 26L with added fundamental PMS design components

It should be noticed that the PMS serving RWY 26R, primarily serving - much fewer - traffic from north, received a consequently smaller open angle and radius of the SLs (not shown): This design step is subject to the inner loop in Figure 4. Prior, the second step is to locate the respective merge points (MP): As further depicted in Figure 6, the respective cost minimization function leads to an off-set location relative to the extended runway center line, while showing a smaller intersection angle as suggested in [31]. The following Figure 7 depicts the cost function model for this second optimization loop, highlighting a higher discretization level applied to the solving process to allow for precise MP positioning:

Concerning ICAO PANS OPS guidance [31], the objective function yields a quite short intermediate approach segment length for runway 26R (2.5 NM, ICAO minimum for the selected intersection angle) for noise protection reasons (detouring the city of Eilenburg, also shown in Figure 7). As a note, much higher costs would have been expected if the current trombone structure (see AIP) applies, as computations showed.

Figure 7: Use case EDDP Step 2: MP optimization for RWY 26L

In comparison to the PMS design of e.g., OSL, we derived a much lower radius r and a larger opening angle Θ for the SL. Especially for western approaches via GOXLI or TAVSO, this allows for rather direct links from Entry Point (EP) to the MP and thus for higher HFE specifically at non-peak traffic times, where direct routes to the MP are becoming crucial for system acceptance.

V. PMS DESIGN VERIFICATION

The final step of the PMS design optimization consists of the verification steps, that begin with using the ABMS [2, 34, 35] (see Figure 4).

During the optimization process on which the weights $w_1 = w_2 = 0.15$, and $w_3 = 0.7$ for noise emissions were applied, the three design candidates 1-3 (“nominal”, “small”, resp. “narrow”) with varying Θ and radius, but with identical merge points (MP) at “Pos1” were found close to optimal with the following parameter:

TABLE I. Design Parameter for all candidate Solutions

s	Design Parameter		
	r [NM]	MP	Θ [°]
Nominal Design - 1	14/16	Pos 1	135
Small Design - 2	11/13	Pos 1	135°
Narrow Design - 3	18/20	Pos 1	75

Normal and Small Design reflect near optimal solutions regarding efficiency and capacity, whereas the Narrow Design have slightly higher costs, and differ in terms of Θ and radius for the southern PMS, runway in use 26L. The Small Design comes with a smaller radius compared to the Nominal Design, whereas the Narrow Design has a larger radius, but smaller Θ . The current trombone design always serves as a reference.

It may further be noted that the validation strategy does not yet include VFE at full extent, limited to preselected SL altitudes, subject to ongoing research on CDO, see section VI.

All three designs were, however, Monte-Carlo simulated with the identical traffic sample as depicted in Figure 5. Altogether 300 simulation runs per design were performed assuming pre-sequenced traffic (FCFS) prior entering the simulation. Figure 8 shows the corresponding flight tracks (yellow) across the PMS per simulation run. The vertical constraints as simplified VFE proxy are depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 8: EDDP: Flight altitude allocation – Nominal Design - 1

The simulated trajectories were analyzed towards achieved performance: first efficiency (average path length) and second capacity (delay) of the candidate designs. For better interpretability, we added the EUROCONTROL proxy *additional Arrival Sequencing and Metering (ASMA) time* [36] to score PMS efficiency, which was consecutively converted into absolute TMA track length flown (see TABLE 1). Allover, it becomes evident that many aircraft approach from south, forming an asymmetric demand pattern, what is typical for hubs with a dedicated operational runway concept, leading in our model to differing design outcomes for the respective PMS, also including a priority for the southern runway for local ground handling efficiency reasons. It may also be noticed, that the ABMS does not allow for radar vectors outside the PMS, strictly managed flight profiles are assumed. This tendentially leads to a conservative (excessive) track milage assessment, affecting horizontal flight efficiency (HFE). Even though not being operationally representative today, this reflects the fundamental

PMS design concept aiming for purely managed flight operations, specifically valuable for CDO applications.

Figure 9: Use case EDDP: Verification Step using ABMS for three candidate designs (top to bottom: Nominal- 1, Small - 2, Narrow - 3),

Further, we introduce the metric *holding rate*, which expresses the quote of aircraft not getting a clearance to proceed to MP while flying along the allocated SL compared to all inbound aircraft in the simulation. This proxy documents any periods during which the capacity of all available SL was not sufficient to satisfy the demand. Based on this proxy, we conclude that Design 3, despite requiring less airspace, always reaches the required capacity, with a holding rate below 0.5 % (see Figure 10, lower part). However, it delivers reduced operational efficiency: The additional ASMA time (see Figure 10, upper part) falls significantly behind the one of the other two designs.

Design 2 consists of SLs at a lower altitude compared to Design 1 and 3. Consequently, we concluded higher noise emissions, and select Design 1 and 3 as preferred designs, subject to the 2nd verification step consisting of a detailed noise assessment: Design 3 may qualitatively come with advantages regarding noise immissions, as SLs are located at a higher altitude. However, demographic data may overrule this effect.

Figure 10: EDDP - additional ASMA time and holding rates, all designs

TABLE II. Average values for efficiency proxies, all designs

	Averages, efficiency proxies, all Designs	
	Additional ASMA time [min]	PMS track length [NM]
Nominal Design - 1	2.71	68.78
Small Design - 2	2.53	68.19
Narrow Design - 3	5.79	80.67

The additional ASMA time found for the narrow Design - 2 due to the long PM to SL leg (high r value). It also delivers the weakest performance on punctuality while still fulfilling the capacity requirements set out. As such, the nominal Design - 1 is considered most favorable within all designs studied.

Figure 11 further depicts the noise immissions for the highest ranked nominal Design - 1 regarding capacity and efficiency (Figure 10). Design - 1 was confirmed in that second verification step to also deliver good results here thus generating the best overall performance given the pre-set weighting. TABLE III summarizes the noise assessment with reference to the current trombone system in terms of altered affected inhabitants per noise pressure level: The target PMS design is producing similar sizes of noise affected areas but reduces the number of affected inhabitants by up to 30% in low pressure regimes, i.e. app. 15 NM away from the airport. This is intuitive, since the geometric design differences weigh in only at this distance. Regarding flight efficiency, the absolute track miles were converted into fuel consumption, assuming ANP standard vertical profiles. TABLE III depicts a reduction of -20%.

Figure 11: Use case EDDP: Noise Assessment for PMS Design 1

TABLE III. Noise immissions, nominal Design - 1, compared to current trombone procedure at EDDP

L _{Night} [dB(A)]	Noise Immissions – Nominal Design - 1 (vs. trombone)	
	Area [km ²]	Inhabitants
35-39	577 (691)	45,347 (75,295)
40-44	309 (303)	21,005 (22,301)
45-49	167 (165)	8,199 (8,277)
50-54	68 (67)	5,615 (5,589)
55-59	26 (26)	741 (719)
60-64	9 (9)	6 (6)
65-69	3 (3)	0 (0)
70-74	0.95 (0,96)	0 (0)
75-79	0.37 (0,37)	0 (0)
total	1,160 (1,266)	80,913 (112,187)

TABLE IV. Fuel burnt per approach, Nominal Design - 1, compared to current trombone procedure at EDDP

RWY [kg/app]	Fuel consumption – Nominal Design - 1 vs. trombone	
	Nominal Design - 1	Trombone
RWY 08L	753	943
RWY 08R	878	1013
RWY 26L	826	933
RWY 26R	792	1000

The results clearly indicate the Nominal Design - 1 is not only providing the highest performance of all three designs, but is also outperforming the reference Trombone design.

VI. DISCUSSION AND OUTLOOK

The presented PMS design philosophy – applied to the use case EDDP - showed competitive performance for all targeted areas efficiency (ASMA time/minimum path length, fuel consumption), capacity (holding rate) and noise (affected inhabitants). Further, systematic concept assessment towards optimization benchmarks is however still to be completed. We are further clear that pre-sequencing of the traffic upstream the PMS entry points is key to further PMS and runway-system utilization potential unlocking and beyond in terms of e.g., balancing APP and ACC traffic load and ATCO workload. This requires precise flight intent information: Efficient flight execution relies on accurate reference data e.g., referring to previous flight legs or to airport and/or enroute slot and weather information. Due to the various key performance areas set out by the 2020 European Air Traffic Management (ATM) Master Plan, optimal aircraft trajectories shall satisfy inherently

multiple and partly competitive objectives as given by f_i through f_3 in this study. A variety of models and input data are required to generate a trajectory, such as aircraft performance models (APM) building primarily on the physical Equations of Motion (EoM) specific to each aircraft/engine type combination, and meteorological forecasts to correctly consider the ambient conditions. These models and input data contain errors and noise by default [37], and as such they bring uncertainty to trajectory computation and related optimization. So far however, aircraft trajectory building has conventionally been carried out in deterministic frameworks solving the problem for a ‘true’ condition (i.e., given weather in the PMS environment). Yet, e.g., incorrect wind prediction deteriorates ground speed calculation, resulting in faulty arrival times, called Along Track Uncertainty (ATU). ATU negatively affects traffic predictability and consequently sequencing and spacing during approach. Consequently, wider aircraft separation for the most probable aircraft sequence beyond the MP is usually applied to grant safe operations. Robust trajectory optimization is considered the next complementary step for the presented research to include such uncertainties. All trajectory optimization approaches must consider aircraft kinetics by dealing with the EoM, formulated as differential equations. Optimal Control (OC) has achieved a prominent role in dealing with vehicle kinetics by considering these equations in their dynamic constraints and searches for a control to reach optimality.

To solve the OC problem, we relax the problem through discrete variable representation using a Pseudo-spectral (PS) method. The robust trajectory optimization avoids deteriorate costs and violation of operational limitations (e.g., speed/altitude limitations) even under weather uncertainties. The method does also incorporate a detailed speed brake model which considers non-clean aircraft configurations during descent. We propose this concept to be integrated into sequencing and spacing upstream the optimized PMS design. We combine two optimization strategies, a) a vertical robust trajectory optimization across the PMS (inner loop) and b) a robust sequence at the MP (outer loop), see Figure 12:

Figure 12: Hybrid optimization consisting of a robust trajectory search (inner loop) and a corresponding sequence at MP (outer loop)

Descent/approach trajectories are calculated for each aircraft based on the robust OC inner optimization. The optimal arrival times of each aircraft at the metering/merging FIX ($t_{FIX}^1, \dots, t_{FIX}^N$) are determined in the outer loop, computing the optimal CTAs ($t_{CTA}^1, \dots, t_{CTA}^N$) using MIP. The optimized CTA values are fed back to the inner loop, potentially initiating a trajectory re-optimization while setting CTAs to RTAs for each aircraft. As $t_{FIX}^1, \dots, t_{FIX}^N$ have variation due to the 4D positional uncertainty, the RTAs are imposed as the expected arrival time: $\mathbb{E}(t_{FIX}^1) = t_{RTA}^1, \dots, \mathbb{E}(t_{FIX}^N) = t_{RTA}^N$. In addition, the constraints

also include the required separation at the MP. We accommodate various objectives, such as maximum throughput, minimum operational cost, or minimum offset between sequenced and ‘user-preferred’ trajectories. We are aware that the complexity of the model increases with these additional steps remarkably. We tend to master this aspect by keeping the fundamental concepts, optimization and ABMS disjoint to allow for stepwise verification and validation.

We believe that this addendum to the presented design model designed this way will leverage the inherent potential of the PMS concept vertically to allow for CDO executions even under instable weather conditions and moderate to high traffic demand.

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